

[Biomarker Analytical Laboratories](#)

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Title: SOP to prepare the Vanquish Duo for dual LC system (Thermo Fisher Scientific) prior to analysis.

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Modules of Vanquish Duo for dual LC system

Solvent rack, Top and Bottom Binary Pump H (VH-P10-A-02), Dual Split Sampler HT (VH-A40-A-02), System Base (VF-S02-A-02), and Left and Right Column Compartment H (VH-C10-A-02)

Important

- Use UCL/MS grade solvents and water (Biosolve Chimie SARL), formic acid (Optima, LC/MS grade).
- Always use the corresponding precolumn to the column.
- Always adjust the needle stroke which differs for vials and well plates.
- SW: Xcalibur 4.7.69.37, Thermo Scientific for SII Xcalibur 1.7.0.468, optionally Chromeleon 7.3.1.

To turn ON/OFF the Vanquish LC system

1. To turn on the LC, press the system power button of the Vanquish system base (front left) and then the main power switch of each module located at the back. Verify that sampler is turned on before the pump flow is on and pressure builds up.
2. If not, turn on the PC and
 - a) For Xcalibur: By clicking the *blue X* icon, open Xcalibur and go to Instrument Setup. At Thermo Xcalibur Instrument Setup window, open the SII Xcalibur and check Direct Control to monitor and purge the propriate LC modules.
 - b) For Chromeleon: click the *Chromeleon* icon to open Chromeleon Console and go to Instrument section, there check the LC bookmark to monitor and purge propriate LC modules.
3. To turn off the LC, close all LC controlling software, press the system power button of the Vanquish system base (front left) and then main power switch of each module located at the back.

To purge the pumps

Pump purging is used to remove air bubbles that might be trapped in the system and when the different solvents are changed for analysis.

1. Open the **Pump_Bottom** ePanel and check the **Module Connection**.
2. For **Pump - More Options**, check the Flow of 5.000 (ml/min) and the Time of 300 (s) is set.
3. For **Eluent**, determine the percentage to be delivered by solvent B (% B) while solvent A (% A) delivers the remaining portion automatically. Set **50.0 (%)** for % B and **50.0 (%)** for % A.
4. For **Eluent Selection**, select the line to be purged by setting **%A_Selector** to **%A1**, **%A2** or **%A3** for channel A as well as **%B_Selector** to **%B1**, **%B2** or **%B3** for channel B.
5. To purge pumps
 - a) check the line channels are placed in proper solvent containers
 - b) set **50.0** and **50.0** for % B and % A
 - c) purge channels **A1/B1** via **Commands** section by ticking the boxes to make Motor: ON and Purge: ON while they become green signed

- d) after a 5-min (300 secs) purge run through **A1/B1**, continue by purging the **A2/B2** and the **A3/B3** channels.
 - e) Additionally, purge by **100.0** and **0.0** for % **B** and % **A** or *vice versa* settings for a 5-min period. Repeat the procedure as needed.
6. Following the **Pump_Bottom** purge, proceed the **Pump_Top** in the same way.

To wash needle and purge needle wash of the dual sampler

For the dual split sampler, i.e.: SampleLeft and SampleRight, there are two needle wash systems each using separate wash liquid. Prior to filling the needle wash reservoir, rinse it thoroughly without the presence of particles, dust or algae.

Use needle wash liquid compatible with your application, e.g. 50 % methanol or 50 % acetonitrile.

To Wash Needle

1. For the **SampleLeft** ePanel in the **Needle Wash** section, set 15.0 (s) and use the Wash Needle button to wash it. Repeat the procedure as needed.
2. Audit Trails notes that process *has started* as well as *has finished*.
3. Following the **SampleLeft** needle wash, proceed the **SampleRight** in the same way.

To Purge Needle Wash

Usually purge speed starts at 140.0 $\mu\text{L/s}$, once passes 1 min, it stops at 24.0 $\mu\text{L/s}$.

1. For the **SampleLeft** ePanel in the **Needle Wash** section, use Purge Needle Wash button to purge it. Repeat the procedure as needed.
2. Following the **SampleLeft** purge, proceed to the **SampleRight** in the same way.

Seal Wash System

The flow path of seal wash system passes automatically through the metering device head in autosampler and the pump heads in pump. For the VH-based autosamplers and pumps, use 75% isopropanol in water and 0.1% formic acid as seal wash liquid.

Prior to filling the seal wash reservoir, rinse it thoroughly without the presence of particles, dust or algae.

1. Regularly check the reservoir bottle.
2. If the seal wash runs out, prepare the new one by mixing 750 mL of isopropanol, 250 mL of water and 1 mL of formic acid.

Prior to chromatographic analysis

1. For the **ColumnComp_L** and the **ColumnComp_R** module, unscrew the line tubing and replace the adapter by the column with precolumn aligned with a flow direction.
2. Let the column with precolumn equilibrated for a certain period prior to chromatographic analysis.
3. Since the analysis finishes, follow this procedure with reservoirs containing water and organic solvent without any additives to remove mobile phase out of the column with precolumn and the line tubing of the LC.
4. To store the chromatographic column, check the manufacturer's recommendation.